

SZ-HB-II-02-04 Completing and sharing a course with other teachers via an OER platform

Author	@Ricarda Peil ; @Julia Victoria Dinier ; @Alexander Schröter ; @Julia Lehmler ; @Tara-marie Endries ; @Sönke Erdmann (original German version) @Jan Martin Kauter ; @Tara-Marie Endries ; @Emily Penk (English translation)
Doi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15261192
ID	SZ-HB-II-02-04
Title	Completing and sharing a course with other teachers via an OER platform
Educational area	#Higher-education
Persona	P: Emil - Professor https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13684426
Short description	Emil compiles materials for his course offering, prepares them for Moodle, and publishes the course with metadata and a license for reuse.
Result	The course is created with Moodle, is searchable and reusable.
Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Problem scenario• Activity scenario<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Part 1: "Collect materials and documents"• Part 2: "Fill the Moodle course"
Preconditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Emil is registered at BIRD• Emil is logged in to BIRD
Components	#workspace
Services / tools	#moodle

Problem scenario

Introduction

Emil Larssen, a dedicated professor of German studies, has spent several years developing and continuously refining a comprehensive course on 19th-century German literature, which he has made available as a course on the Moodle learning management System (LMS). He will no longer be offering this course at his university. Emil does not want his accumulated knowledge and his specific course offering to disappear; rather, he wants it to continue to exist as an open educational resource (OER). Emil likes the idea of OER because he himself benefits from the free availability of educational materials. Furthermore, this opens up the possibility for other teachers to further develop and use the course. This would have helped him during his early years as a lecturer.

Problem definition

To reach as many interested people as possible with his course, Emil is considering developing it both as a guide for lecturers and as a self-study resource for students. Because Emil aims for the continued use of his course, he needs to ensure it can be found quickly and easily. To do this, he needs to properly tag and describe his content. He considers several criteria that best describe his course and determines under which conditions, i.e., under which license, the course can be reused.

Background and context

Emil places great importance on the quality and availability of online educational resources. Teaching methods have changed significantly in recent years, so the reuse of courses and materials should be better supported. In the context of German studies, it is common to offer content that delves deeply into literary history and analysis: long lists of secondary literature, numerous references and citations. Emil has long recognized that open digital learning platforms such as Moodle, OPAL, or ILIAS offer a fantastic opportunity to share and disseminate teaching materials and thus reach many interested students from other institutions or disciplines. Unfortunately, very few such platforms are open and therefore accessible to everyone. Consequently, sharing has so far mainly occurred through personal contacts.

Impact of the problem (on the Persona)

Due to the restructuring of his course offerings and the additional target group of instructors (in addition to learners), Emil needs to come up with new or supplementary keywords. Since he plans to publish his offerings as an OER resource, he needs to create further descriptive metadata, which he hasn't had to do in this way before. Without a standardized, i.e., standards-based, and supported input form, this is complicated.

If Emil's course isn't described correctly, in the short and medium term, it might not be found and used by other instructors, which limits the influence and reach of his teaching content. His work receives less visibility. In the long term, however, this could also mean that valuable educational resources remain unused and the opportunities for collaboration and knowledge exchange among instructors are limited. Therefore, Emil wants to make his own resources more accessible.

Pre BIRD attempts at a solution

Until now, Emil has shared his teaching materials and course content for instructors through informal networks within the academic community via personal contacts. If there

was interest in his course, he provided the materials via email. However, this approach was time-consuming, complicated in terms of data handling, and lacked the mutual support and exchange that Emil desires.

For these reasons, he has repeatedly looked for alternatives but he has not found an effective way to share entire LMS courses — specifically Moodle courses — together with metadata and licensing Information. Emil has indeed used the course search function on moodle.net and searched open learning platforms like “WirLernenOnline” for nearly identical offerings to his, but found nothing. This reinforces his decision to make his own course available.

Activity scenario

Part 1: "Collect materials and documents"

Step 1: Emil opens the Moodle course via the BIRD interface on the open Moodle/LMS system, which had been set up for him by the person responsible for his Course “German Literature of the 19th Century”. He has already uploaded a copy of his old Moodle course there, which he had previously saved locally. Now he needs to complete and expand it and upload additional materials.

Step 2: He opens BIRD and navigates to his workspace. There he creates a new project, which he calls “*Preparation for the Seminar German Literature of the 19th Century – OER*”.

Step 3: In the project, Emil creates different folders for the “slides”, the “literature” and the “tasks” in order to store them in a structured way and be able to process them further.

Step 4: Emil places the prepared and tested slides, which he also uses for his in-person seminars, into the "Slides" folder. He checked the copyright of all content beforehand and removed all files that were not freely licensed or created by him.

Step 5: He places the bibliography, as well as important articles and links to other online resources, in the "Literature" folder. Emil places the tasks as PDFs, as well as a formative and a summative assessment for the self-study course, in the "Tasks" folder.

Step 6: After Emil has structured all the materials for the Moodle course and gathered them in one place, he can now focus on populating the Moodle Course.

Part 2: "Fill the Moodle course"

Step 1: Emil opens the created course in Moodle.

Step 2: Emil transfers the materials from the BIRD workspace and first finalizes the version of the course for the other university lecturers, which he wants to make available as a complete Moodle course as OER. He then exports the course as a Moodle file and turns to preparing the version for learners.

Step 3: He adds the planned assessments and other instructions, and changes the

course layout to the more appealing tile view. He then configures the system so that a [Moodle badge](#) can be awarded upon successful course completion. Learners can then easily transfer this badge to their data wallet.

Step 4: Emil chooses Creative Commons **BY-NC-SA 4.0** as the license for the course, which allows use and distribution under the same conditions and for non-commercial use.

Step 5: Emil is aware that he can only successfully make the course available if it can later be found using the correct criteria. Therefore, he still needs to add a description and additional metadata to his Course. To ensure he doesn't forget anything and doesn't have to search for long when filling out the form, he uses the BIRD data room plug-in.

Step 6: Emil uses the data room plug-in in BIRD. This is especially helpful for Emil. Data entry can be supported by autofill and automatic suggestions based on his BIRD profile. This allows Emil to expand the reach of his educational offerings with minimal effort.

Step 7: He considers several criteria that best describe his course and how it can be used or under what conditions it may be reused. Emil wants to use the following criteria: "19th-century literature", "lecture", "analysis", "recommended semester".

Step 8: In order to be able to represent not only the specified content-related learning objectives, but also the didactic and cognitive learning objectives in the metadata, Emil uses the possibility of filling metadata such as "time management", "differentiated perception", "independent thinking ability", "imagination" and "creativity" with attributes.

Step 9: Emil publishes the course on the open Moodle system of the respective institution and publishes the metadata in the data room, thus making it discoverable via the LearningPathfinder.

Step 10: Finally, Emil wants to facilitate reuse of the course by additionally uploading the previously exported course to WirLernenOnline and providing metadata via the BIRD Moodle plugin.

*Humboldt University of Berlin does not have an open learning management system at the time of publication. Other universities already offer this service (see: [Home | Open.UP](#), [Home | OpenMoodle](#)).